

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

Prof. dr Petar Bulat

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- *President of the 13th STC Congress*

Petar Bulat

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- *President of the CSC*
- *of the 13th STC Congress*

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ETIL KARBAMAT U RAKIJAMA OD VOĆA - PROCENA RIZIKA ZA ZDRAVLJE

TOXICOLOGICAL
RISK ASSESSMENT

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Najnovija istraživanja Svetske zdravstvene organizacije pokazala su da se svake godine 3 miliona smrtnih ishoda javi kao direktna posledica konzumiranja alkoholnih pića, zbog prisustva jedinjenja koja mogu imati potencijalno karcinogeni efekat, među kojima je i etil karbamat (EC). Ciljevi rada su određivanje sadržaja EC u uzorcima rakija od različitih vrsta voća, poređenje dobijenih vrednosti sa limitom preporučenim od strane Međunarodne alijanse za odgovorno konzumiranje alkohola i komparativna procena zdravstvenog rizika izazvanog konzumiranjem voćnih rakija. Analiza 134 uzorka alkoholnih pića sa tržišta Republike Srbije sprovedena je primenom GC-MS.

Rizik je procenjen izračunavanjem margine izloženosti (MOE) i karcinogenog rizika tokom životnog veka, na osnovu faktora nagiba za oralnu toksičnost (1), odnosno bezbedne doze (2). U 95% uzoraka sadržaj EC je bio iznad limita od 0,4 mg/L. Uočen je statistički značajno viši sadržaj EC u rakijama od šljive. Za muškarce, 98% uzoraka je pokazalo MOE vrednosti ispod dozvoljenog limita od 10000 pri prosečnoj potrošnji alkohola, odnosno 100% kod hroničnog visokog unosa alkohola, dok je za žene to iznosilo od 79% pri prosečnoj potrošnji do 99% za visoki unos. Zavisno od primenjenog pristupa proceni, utvrđeno je da već pri prosečnoj potrošnji: (1) nijedan uzorak nema zanemarljiv karcinogeni efekat, nezavisno od pola, odnosno (2) više od 88% uzoraka predstavlja rizik po zdravlje žena, odnosno 99% po zdravlje muškaraca. Istraživanje je pokazalo prisustvo značajnih koncentracija EC u voćnim rakijama. Potrebno je primeniti mere u toku proizvodnje u cilju smanjenja nastanka EC i zakonski regulisati maksimalno dozvoljenu koncentraciju etil karbamata u rakijama.

KLJUČNE REČI: etil karbamat, MOE, karcinogeni rizik, voćne rakije

ETHYL CARBAMATE IN FRUIT SPIRITS - HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT

TOXICOLOGICAL
RISK ASSESSMENT

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The latest World Health Organization research revealed that 3 million deaths every year result from harmful use of alcohol, due to the presence of compounds, including ethyl carbamate (EC), that can have potentially carcinogenic effect. The aims of this study are determination of EC content in fruit spirits, comparison of the obtained values with the limit proposed by the International Alliance for Responsible Alcohol Consumption and comparative health risk assessment caused by the fruit spirits consumption. Fruit spirit samples (134, Republic of Serbia) were analyzed using GC-MS. Risk was assessed using the margin of exposure (MOE) and excess lifetime cancer risk approach, based on the oral slope factor (1) or virtually safe dose (2). The EC content was above limit of 0.4 mg/L in 95% of samples. Higher content in plum spirits was statistically significant.

For men, 98% of the samples showed MOE values below the limit of 10 000 for average consumption, i.e., 100% for chronic heavy drinkers, while for women it ranged from 79% for average consumption to 99% for chronic heavy drinkers. Depending on the approach, already at average consumption: (1) no sample had a negligible cancer risk, regardless of gender; (2) more than 88% of the samples represented a risk to women's health, i.e., 99% to men's health. Research has shown a significant presence of EC in fruit spirits. It is necessary to implement measures during production to prevent the occurrence of EC, as well as legally regulate the maximum allowed concentration of EC in fruit spirits.

KEYWORDS: ethyl carbamate, MOE, carcinogenic risk, fruit spirits